

The use of air entraining/plasticizing admixtures in cement-lime masonry mortars: effects on fresh and hardened mortar properties

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Abstract. Modern day masonry mortars rely on more than just standard constituents, which by definition include binder, aggregates and water. Due to different requirements imposed onto various types of masonry construction, ready mix mortar manufacturers and even masons and labourers on construction sites add certain additives to their mortar formulations. In this study, one standardized admixture is studied – an air entrainer/plasticizer (EN 934-3), coming in two forms – liquid and powder. It is applied to increase the air content and plasticity of cement-lime masonry mortar, formulated in volumetric proportions of 1:1:6 for cement, lime and aggregates. The dosage of admixtures is gradually increased starting with the manufacturer's recommendations until the excessive air entrainment is achieved in order to determine the optimal dosage. Fresh mortar properties, including consistency, air content and bulk density are used to assess the enhancement of mortar influenced by the addition of the admixture, whereas compressive and flexural testing is performed at 7 and 28 days to monitor the disadvantages brought by reducing density. The results of this study reveal that the efficacy of a liquid admixture is better than that of a powdered air entrainer/plasticizer, albeit it being more difficult to use accurately. In both cases, higher dosage than manufacturer's recommendations was required to reach satisfactory improvement of the fresh mortar structure, which resulted in a mixing water reduction, increased air content and reduced bulk density. That subsequently influenced the decreased strength, although optimally formulated mortars adhered to their strength class requirements.

1 Background

Modern construction industry revolves around a selection of established materials, namely concrete, steel, masonry, timber and glass [1]. Convenient construction of durable buildings often calls for time-efficient and uncomplicated methods, which masonry fits well [2].

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Masonry often involves two main components – a building block and a mortar, which acts as the glue used in joining blocks together. The latter component is rather crucial at construction stage, since it undergoes a substantial change from dry material, to fresh and malleable substance, to a hardened layer whose properties are important in the context of a masonry wall.

1.1 Cement-lime masonry mortars

Cement is the popular choice as the binding material in mortars for masonry purposes, but lime has undeniably been instrumental in such application for millennia [3]. The combination of both binders is a viable option for modern masonry construction, and when mixed in different proportions, cement-lime binders cover a range of structural and non-structural applications [4,5]. Based on European practice documented in some national annexes to Eurocode 6 [6] and also North American [7] and Indian [8] experience, a mortar comprised of 1 volumetric part of cement, 1 part of lime, and 6 parts of aggregates can be considered a general purpose mortar suitable for both load bearing and non-load bearing use cases.

Recent research efforts have examined the viability of 1:1:6 cement:lime:sand mortar mixtures in masonry [9–14]. Such formulation is prescribed to produce mortars with 28 day compressive strength of at least 5 MPa [6–8] and this prediction was corroborated by various researchers [9,11,14]. However, compressive strength of a masonry mortar is only of importance after structural blocks have been laid using such mortar, and at construction stage, the fresh mortar performance is of primary significance. Even though many studies have reported mixing water requirements of 1:1:6 mortars, there is rather limited data on the air contents in such mortars [15], although for non-air-entrained masonry mortars it is found to be in range of 4-8% [16], which may not be sufficient from different perspectives.

1.2 Air entraining/plasticizing admixtures for masonry mortars

The purpose of air entrainment in masonry mortars is associated with increased durability in cases of freeze-thaw actions [17]. However, formation of microscopic air voids also produces a plasticizing effect in fresh mortars, thus reducing the mixing water requirement. Furthermore, since fresh mortar contains more air, its bulk density is reduced. These effects are favourable from the point of view of professionals applying them during construction stages, as they work with lighter material, but that also presents financial and environmental benefits due to reduced raw material consumption required for masonry wall construction.

Previous research has demonstrated that modification of masonry mortars using air entraining additives has significant effects on both fresh and hardened mortar properties. Increased air content and decreased bulk density, along with a decrease in mechanical performance have been reported by different authors [18–20]. Traditionally assumed plasticizing effect of lime in cement-based mortars [21], on the other hand, has been shown to be incomparable to that of an air entraining/plasticizing admixture [22]. Furthermore, the effect of such admixtures has not been extensively studied in blended cement-lime mortars, particularly the 1:1:6 formulation.

1.3 Aim and objectives of the study

This article aims to further the understanding of the influence chemical additives can have on masonry mortars. To achieve such goal, the 1:1:6 masonry mortar is studied in combination with two different air entraining/plasticizing admixtures. Admixture-induced mortar modifications are assessed by testing fresh and hardened mortar properties.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Binding materials

Portland-limestone cement CEM II/A-L 32.5 R, complying with EN 197-1 [23], and hydrated lime CL90 S, complying with EN 459-1 [24] were used in this study.

2.2 Aggregates

Silicious aggregates from SIBELCO [25] were custom-tailored for a suitable granulometry (Fig.1.), producing an appropriate reference mortar, which exhibited no excessive bleeding, nor segregation. This particle size distribution also fits within the limits established by BS 1199 and 1200 [26], adopted by the SUBLime consortium [27].

Fig. 1. Particle size distribution of mortar aggregates

2.3 Air entraining/plasticizing admixtures

Two air entraining/plasticizing admixtures, both conforming to EN 934-3 [28] were used in this research:

- Powdered admixture Febmix DH from Sika [29];
- Concentrated liquid admixture OPTI-mix from Sika [30].

Manufacturer's recommended dosages for the OPTI-mix are 5-10 ml for 50 kg of cement, whereas 15 g of Febmix should be used for 25 kg of cement. In the latter case, the combination of cement and lime in the binder is permitted, although it is not recommended in the former. Febmix is referred to as powdered admixture, and OPTI-mix – as liquid admixture herein.

In this study, the manufacturer's recommended dosages were applied in relation to the total amount of binder (cement and lime) and were then increased incrementally.

2.4 Mix design

The mix designs of all studied mortars are presented in Table 1. All mortars contained roughly 10% of cement, 4% of lime and 86% of aggregates by mass, a ratio which was translated from the 1:1:6 volumetric composition using bulk densities of all components. In

addition to the reference mortar (Ref), air-entrained mortars were produced using variable dosages of powdered liquid admixtures, starting from the minimum dose. For the powdered admixture, the absolute mass increments correspond to 0.06% (manufacturer's recommendation), 0.1%, 0.2% and 0.3% of the total binder mass. In case of the liquid admixture, the dosage could only be expressed in millilitres, since it was mixed together with mixing water, rather than the dry components, such as the powdered additive.

Table 1. Mix designs of cement-lime mortars with different admixtures

Mortar name	Dry components [g]			Liquid [ml]		W/B
	Cement	Lime	Aggregates	Febmix	OPTI-mix	
Ref	348	140	3000	-	-	1.10
Pow 1				0.29	-	1.10
Pow 2				0.49	-	1.00
Pow 3				0.98	-	0.93
Pow 4				1.47	-	0.88
Liq 1				-	0.05	1.05
Liq 2				-	0.10	0.98
Liq 3				-	0.15	0.91
Liq 4				-	0.20	0.88

2.5 Fresh properties

The required amount of mixing water, or the water to binder ratio (W/B in Table 1) was determined based on the flow table value of 175 ± 10 mm, tested according to EN 1015-3 [31].

Fresh bulk density of mortars was tested according to EN 1015-6 [32] and air content according to EN 1015-7 [33].

2.6 Hardened properties

Compressive strength of all mortars was determined at the ages of 7 and 28 days, in accordance with EN 1015-11 [34]. Furthermore, bulk density of hardened mortars was calculated using prismatic specimen dimensions and respective mortar weights at specified ages to assess the stability of entrained air and its effects on the mechanical behaviour of cement-lime mortars.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Fresh mortar performance

All studied mortars have been formulated to reach similar consistency by flow table value, yet their fresh state was completely different, as indicated by the bulk density and air content summarized in Table 2, but also overall workability and cohesiveness of the mix, which were drastically improved starting with the admixture amounts in Pow 2 and Liq 2 mortars. The latter improvement was assessed qualitatively by the authors of this study.

However, manufacturer's recommended minimum dosage of powdered admixture (Pow 1 mortar) did not produce sufficient air entrainment, which is expected to be around 14-20% [28]. The dosage of Pow 2 mortar was optimal in this regard, whereas both Pow 3 and Pow 4 mortars demonstrated air entrainment levels above 20%.

Similar behaviour was observed in the mortars with liquid admixture, although manufacturer's recommended higher dosage was optimal to produce a mortar with 16% of

entrained air – Liq 2. Other dosages were either insufficient as in the case of Liq 1, or excessive – Liq 3 and Liq 4.

Nonetheless, since the dosages were tailored to the total amount of binder, rather than only cement, both optimal mixes actually exceeded the recommended dosages.

Table 2. Fresh mortar properties

Mortar name	Flow [mm]	Bulk Density [kg/m ³]	Air content
Ref	174	2095	5%
Pow 1	176	2018	8%
Pow 2	176	1865	16%
Pow 3	173	1777	21%
Pow 4	171	1708	24%
Liq 1	175	1978	10%
Liq 2	174	1862	16%
Liq 3	171	1775	22%
Liq 4	172	1709	25%

By superimposing the effects of both admixtures in Fig. 2, almost no discernible differences could be demonstrated. Whilst all the mortars were produced to have a flow in the range of 171-176 mm (Table 2), both the plasticizing effect (Fig.2. a) and the increase in air content (Fig.2. b) were impacted similarly by two types of admixture. The only case without the expected plasticizing action was for the Pow 1 mortar, which offered no reduction in the mixing water demand, but only a higher air content. Otherwise, all mortars have shown the expected behaviour.

Fig. 2. Comparison of a) water to binder ratio, and b) air content of mortars with increasing dosage of admixtures

Despite the similarities in overall effectiveness in case of fresh state modification, both admixtures are vastly different in their application. Powdered admixture is favourable for its ease of use, especially when considering factory produced ready to mix masonry mortars, which dominate the masonry market. However, in small-scale applications it could be difficult to ensure the complete blending of the additive with the rest of the dry material and therefore, inhomogeneities could occur. This is largely eliminated in the case of liquid admixture, which is first mixed with water, and then is well-distributed in the fresh mortar during mixing. However, since dosage of such admixture needs to be determined based on the size of the batch and calculated against the total water amount, it may not be an optimal choice for large scale construction due to potential quality control issues.

3.2 Hardened mortar performance

At respective ages of 7 and 28 days, all the studied mortars were subjected to dimensional measurement, weighing and mechanical testing. The results obtained are presented in Table 3.

The reduction of bulk density of the hardened mortars was influenced by the air entrainment in the fresh mortar state, with all air-entrained mortars being lighter than the reference one. Yet, while mortars with both powdered and liquid admixtures had similar density and air content in the fresh state, i.e. Pow 2 and Liq 2 in Table 2, in the hardened state, Liq 1 – 4 mortars have demonstrated lower densities than Pow 1 – 4 mortars. This might indicate that stability of microscopic air bubbles induced by the dry additive is lower than stability of liquid admixture bubbles, which could affect the density of mortar matrix during moulding and compaction.

The flexural strength of all mortars with admixtures was somewhat lower than that of the reference mortar at 7 days, with the exception of Pow 4 and Liq 3, which had the highest and the lowest flexural strengths, respectively. However, at 28 days, all air-entrained mortars presented flexural strengths lower than the reference mortar, and it generally declined with the increased dosage of both admixtures, although a slight increase was noticed in the case of Pow 4.

Table 3. Hardened properties of mortars tested at 7 and 28 days

	7 days						28 days					
	Bulk density		Flexural strength		Compressive strength		Bulk density		Flexural strength		Compressive strength	
	$\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$	CV	[MPa]	CV	[MPa]	CV	$\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$	CV	[MPa]	CV	[MPa]	CV
Ref	2044	1.3%	1.18	1.7%	3.49	11.5%	1887	0.2%	2.00	9.0%	6.95	4.4%
Pow 1	1964	0.3%	1.09	0.9%	3.08	1.8%	1818	0.3%	1.86	2.2%	6.12	2.1%
Pow 2	1838	1.5%	1.08	5.6%	2.94	0.9%	1725	0.2%	1.71	8.8%	5.04	4.4%
Pow 3	1772	0.6%	1.03	1.5%	2.85	2.3%	1678	0.2%	1.62	2.2%	4.83	2.8%
Pow 4	1726	0.9%	1.19	0.8%	2.88	6.6%	1633	0.5%	1.72	4.7%	4.82	6.0%
Liq 1	1871	0.1%	1.10	3.2%	2.91	2.9%	1754	0.4%	1.87	1.3%	5.84	1.6%
Liq 2	1786	0.7%	1.08	5.6%	2.81	1.5%	1698	0.1%	1.72	0.6%	5.10	1.7%
Liq 3	1734	0.1%	0.98	1.0%	2.78	7.2%	1652	0.1%	1.56	5.8%	4.87	6.7%
Liq 4	1678	0.5%	1.09	3.2%	2.54	6.0%	1593	0.1%	1.48	2.4%	4.69	6.4%

Compressive strength of masonry mortars with admixtures was impacted more severely than their flexural strength. The reduction of compressive strength is represented in relation to the reduction of mortar density to better assess the efficiency of the admixtures – Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Compressive strength vs. bulk density of mortars at 7 and 28 days

The 1:1:6 mortar is formulated to achieve 5 MPa of compressive strength at the age of 28 days, conforming to the M5 mortar strength class [6], which means that the use of air entraining/plasticizing admixtures could be detrimental to mortar performance. Based on Table 3 and Fig. 3, mortars denoted Pow 3 and Pow 4, along with Liq 3 and Liq 4 did not satisfy the strength requirements of the Eurocode 6 and they had higher-than-recommended entrained air contents [28].

However, based on EN 934-3, the minimum required strength of an air-entrained mortar should reach at least 70% that of the non-air-entrained mortar. Whilst Liq 4 mortar, which clearly had the lowest density and therefore the highest air content even in the hardened state, did not satisfy this requirement, both Pow 3 and Pow 4 were very close to this limit (highlighted in Fig. 3.), with Liq 3 mix being slightly above it.

Interestingly, the 70% strength requirement was fully met by all the mortars at 7 days, which indicated that strength gain at the early stages of hardening up to 7 days is affected less severely than in the later stage at 7 to 28 days.

Overall, at both ages of testing, liquid admixture mortars were not significantly different in terms of compressive strength compared to powdered admixture mortars, despite having lower densities.

Hardened behaviour of modified mortars confirms the need to tailor the dosage of admixtures in the fresh state, particularly to not exceed the 20% of entrained air content whilst achieving suitable mechanical properties, as in the case of Pow 2 and Liq 2 mortars.

The previous prediction regarding the difficulty in using powdered admixture for small-scale trials with high confidence was verified as well, as evident from consistently higher densities of all powdered admixture mortars, indicating poorer air bubble stability than in liquid admixture mortars. That could have further implications for the durability of the mortar, which further supports the applicability of dry admixture use in factory-made dry-mix mortars, as opposed to site-made mortars, which could benefit from the liquid admixture use.

4 Conclusions

The use of air entraining/plasticizing admixtures in cement-lime masonry mortars was evaluated from the perspectives relevant to the construction phase, and structural requirements. Considering materials used in this particular study, several findings could be revealed:

- Cement-lime mortars can be successfully air-entrained using powdered or liquid admixtures.
- The dosage required to achieve sufficient entrained air content in 1:1:6 mortar is higher than recommended by the manufacturer.
- The best performance in terms of fresh air entrainment and satisfactory mechanical properties was achieved by using admixture dosages corresponding to Pow 2 and Liq 2 formulations.
- The stability of entrained air is dependent on the physical state of the admixture. Powdered admixture was shown to potentially produce air bubbles of lower stability than liquid admixture.
- Liquid admixtures might be a suitable choice for on-site mortar making, whereas powdered additives could be used more efficiently in a controlled mortar factory environment.

These conclusions are attributed to the studied materials; therefore, further research is needed to ascertain the effects of similar or different admixtures on masonry mortars of various compositions.

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